

Characterization of Macrocellular PCS Propagation Channels in the 1850-1990 MHz Band

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Wideband propagation measurements for Personal Communication Services (PCS) were taken in the 1850-1990 MHz band in three different outdoor macrocellular (cell radii of 5 km) environments: flat rural, hilly rural, and urban high-rise. The data were analyzed to provide a description of the statistical behavior of the impulse responses in each cell. This analysis included RMS delay spread statistics, multipath power statistics, number of paths and path arrival time statistics, and effects of spatial diversity. The number of paths and path arrival time statistics provide particularly useful information in the design of tapped delay line models of the radio channel for PCS applications.

1. INTRODUCTION

This paper discusses a set of impulse response measurements taken in the 1850-1990 MHz band* both to support ongoing channel modelling and simulation efforts as well as to support analytical methods required in the development of new telecommunication services such as Personal Communication Services (PCS) and advanced cellular mobile systems. The measurements were taken in three different cell environments in the Denver, Colorado, area: a flat rural cell, a hilly rural cell, and an urban high-rise cell. The flat rural cell consisted primarily of open spaces and farmland. The foothills of the Rocky Mountains were approximately 45 km west of the center of this cell. Throughout most of the cell, the elevation varied by only about 30 m. The hilly rural cell consisted primarily of open space areas with some valleys and rolling hills. The elevation varied by about 300 m throughout this cell. The foothills of the Rocky Mountains were approximately 5 km west of the center of this cell. The urban high-rise cell was located in downtown Denver and consisted of closely-spaced buildings with heights typically ranging from 25 to 35 stories. The elevation of the terrain throughout this cell varied by about 85 m.

2. MEASUREMENT SYSTEM

The measurements within each cell were made using the Digital Impulse Response Measurement System (patent pending) developed jointly by the Institute for

Telecommunication Sciences and Telesis Technologies Laboratory. This system is comprised of a separate transmitter and receiver. For these measurements, the receiver was placed at the center of the cell in a fixed location and the transmitter was installed in a mini-van. A single, binary phase-shift keyed (BPSK), PN code sequence was transmitted at a 10-Mbit/s rate and a dual-channel receiver employing spatial diversity (with a 15 wavelength separation) was used to receive the transmitted signal. The transmitter power level was set to 50 W effective isotropically radiated power (EIRP). The receiver had a processing gain of 27 dB and a noise figure of approximately 7.5 dB. The maximum measurable delay was 51.1 μ s.

3. MEASUREMENT PROCEDURE

In the rural cells, the receiver was located in a large measurement van and kept at a fixed location. The receive antennas were mounted on a telescoping mast 8.7 m aboveground. In the urban high-rise cell, the receiver was located on the rooftop of a building approximately 103 m aboveground in the center of the high-rise district in downtown Denver. All of the measurements were made within a 5-km radius of the center of each cell, using omnidirectional vertically polarized transmit and receive antennas.

Three primary calibration procedures were performed: frequency calibration, amplitude calibration, and absolute time synchronization. After all of the calibration procedures, the radio frequency spectrum was observed to determine the potential interfering signals in or near the measurement frequency band. The center frequency of the measurement system was set such that any interference from or to existing services would be avoided. An over-the-air test, which was primarily qualitative in nature, was then performed to test the proper functioning of the entire transmitter/receiver measurement system including the antennas and antenna feed cables. Impulse response data were collected simultaneously on both receive channels as the transmitter van travelled along predetermined routes within each cell. The data were taken approximately every 0.7 s as a rapid succession of 10 impulse responses while the transmitter van was moving. Within this

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succession of 10 impulse responses, a time interval of 255.5 μs (5 times the PN code word duration) was used between the beginning of one impulse and the beginning of the next. Spatial distance between each impulse response within the succession of 10 ranged from approximately 0.17 to 0.63 cm (0.01 to 0.04 wavelengths) while that between each succession of 10 impulse responses ranged from 4.66 to 17.26 m (29.8 to 110.5 wavelengths).

4. DATA ANALYSIS METHODS AND RESULTS

The data were analyzed to provide a comprehensive description of the statistical behavior of the impulse responses in each cell. This analysis included maximum delay, mean delay, and RMS delay spread statistics; effects of spatial diversity; multipath power statistics; number of paths and path arrival time statistics; and correlation bandwidth statistics. The results of the analyses of RMS delay spread, spatial diversity, multipath power, and number of paths and path arrival time are presented here for the flat rural and urban high-rise cells only. A more detailed description of all of the analyses, presentation of the results for all cells, and explanation of the entire measurement project is given in [1]. The statistics are formed from data taken in each cell separately. All statistics are computed using the data from one channel only, except for the spatial diversity statistics which inherently rely on the data from both channels. All of the statistics are computed from averaged power delay profiles (PDPs). The PDP is the magnitude squared of the measured complex impulse response. Each averaged PDP (APDP) is an average of the succession of 10 PDPs. This averaging reduces the noise floor and thus improves the interval of discrimination (ID). The ID is the difference in power between the peak value in the PDP and the peak of the noise.

The received signal levels obtained in the measurements tended to be relatively low in some locations due to the long distances between the transmitter and receiver, limited transmitter power as required by the experimental license, and shadow fading. Because of these relatively low signal levels and the presence of multipath, an ID of only 20 dB could be guaranteed from APDPs taken in these locations. Because of this, and in order to treat APDPs of varying IDs on an equivalent basis, only delayed signals within 20 dB of the peak value in the APDP were counted as significant for the computations. To ensure that noise was not included in the statistical computations, an APDP was only considered valid (for inclusion in the statistics) if its ID was 23 dB or greater. This assured that samples of the APDP up to 20 dB below the peak received signal would be actual delayed signals and not noise (by providing a 3-dB buffer between the peak of the noise and the region where the amplitude of delayed signals was considered significant).

In the discussion of the various statistics that follows, the number of valid APDPs within each cell should be kept in

mind. The flat rural cell had 3220 valid APDPs and the urban high-rise cell had 3813 valid APDPs.

4.1 Effects of Spatial Diversity

The effects of spatial diversity can be determined in many ways. The method presented here compares the cumulative distributions of RMS delay spread for Channel 1, for Channel 2, and for the lowest RMS delay spread between both channels (hereafter called the diversity combination). The RMS delay spread was computed as given in [2-5].

Figure 1 shows the cumulative distributions of RMS delay spread for the flat rural (1a) and urban high-rise (1b) cells. For each cell, the cumulative distributions of RMS delay spread are shown for Channel 1, Channel 2, and the diversity combination of the two channels. The urban high-rise cell shows a much higher probability of exceeding RMS delay spread values (up to 1.3 μs) than the flat rural cell. Within each cell, observe that the cumulative distribution for Channel 1 and the cumulative distribution for Channel 2 are nearly identical. This result is to be expected since the cumulative distribution for Channel 1 or Channel 2 is a statistical description of the RMS delay spread behavior in an entire cell over a large number of samples. Therefore, regardless of how the RMS delay spread values compare between a given APDP on Channel 1 and the corresponding APDP formed from PDPs taken simultaneously on Channel 2, the cumulative distributions for each channel separately within a given cell should be quite similar. The cumulative distribution for the diversity combination shows a lower probability of exceeding an RMS delay spread value in both cells than for Channel 1 or Channel 2 separately. This result is most pronounced in the urban high-rise cell. These results suggest that the wideband signals seen on each channel are indeed uncorrelated to some degree. If these signals were correlated, one would expect to see no difference in the cumulative distributions of RMS delay spread between Channel 1, Channel 2, and the diversity combination of the two channels.

4.2 Multipath Power Statistics

The multipath power statistics provide information about the signal amplitude for every delay time for all of the APDPs in a given cell. These statistics include as a function of delay time: average multipath power, peak multipath power, and probability of multipath power exceeding a threshold. Before computation of these statistics, each APDP is normalized by amplitude shifting the entire APDP such that the peak sample in each APDP is set to 0 dB. This allows APDPs of varying total power to be treated on an equivalent basis for the computation of the multipath power statistics.

The average multipath power shows the average power of a delayed signal at a given delay time for the data in each cell.

The peak multipath power shows the largest normalized signal power that was observed at a given delay time for the data in each cell. The last type of multipath power statistic is the probability of multipath power exceeding a threshold. For the data in each cell, these statistics are computed by finding the probability that a delayed signal's power will be greater than a given threshold for each delay time. Four different threshold levels are used: -5 dB, -10 dB, -15 dB, and -20 dB, where 0 dB represents the power of the peak sample in each normalized APDP.

The average multipath power and the peak multipath power vs delay time are shown in Figure 2 for the flat rural (2a) and urban high-rise (2b) cells. The average multipath power curve for the flat rural cell has a narrow peak close to 0 dB that rapidly decreases to -20 dB at about 0.5 μ s of delay. The average multipath power is higher for every delay time out to about 3 μ s in the urban high-rise cell as compared to the flat rural cell. Note that there is a general tendency as the delays get longer in time for the peak amplitudes to decrease. The flat rural cell shows higher peak amplitudes for delay times greater than 15 μ s than the urban high-rise cell. This may occur because the terrain and lack of closely-spaced buildings in the flat rural cell allows for less-obstructed, longer radio paths than in the urban high-rise cell. The urban high-rise cell has higher peak amplitudes for delay times up to about 3 μ s, probably because shorter radio paths are much more prevalent due to closely-spaced buildings.

The threshold statistics vs delay time are displayed in Figure 3 for the flat rural (3a) and urban high-rise (3b) cells. For each graph, the top curve represents the probability of the normalized multipath power exceeding -20 dB. The second, third, and fourth curves from the top represent the probability of the normalized multipath power exceeding -15, -10, and -5 dB, respectively. The urban high-rise cell shows a much higher percentage of APDPs that are above threshold than the flat rural cell. For example, in the urban high-rise cell, 64% of the APDPs have delayed signals above the -20 dB threshold at a delay time of 1 μ s. In the flat rural cell, only 5% of the APDPs have delayed signals above the -20 dB threshold at a delay time of 1 μ s. As the threshold level is increased, the percentage of APDPs above threshold decreases. As an example of this, consider the urban high-rise cell. At a delay time of 2 μ s, 41, 18, 7, and 1% of the APDPs have signals above the -20, -15, -10, and -5 dB thresholds, respectively.

The multipath power statistics show that the urban high-rise cell has by far more multipath components above threshold than the flat rural cell (out to 4 or 5 μ s in delay). These statistics also show that the peak (normalized) multipath power is higher for very long delays (greater than 15 μ s) in the flat rural cell than in the urban high-rise cell.

4.3 Number of Paths and Path Arrival Time Statistics

The goal of the presentation of the statistics in this section is to provide information to assist in the development of impulse response models (primarily tapped delay line models) of the radio channel for PCS. The first type of statistic presented is a cumulative distribution of the number of paths that exceed a threshold (within a 100-ns resolution). A threshold 20 dB below the peak value in each APDP is used. A path is identified in one of two ways. First, if four consecutive samples in the APDP (spaced 25 ns apart) are all above the -20 dB threshold and are continually increasing in power, a path is identified. Second, if a sample in the APDP is of higher power than the next sample, a path is identified. Once a path is identified, three samples (spaced 25 ns apart) are skipped and the search for a new path begins on the next sample (i.e., on the fourth sample from the sample where the last path was identified). Skipping three samples before beginning to look for a new path ensures that no more than one path is identified within the resolution of the measurement system (100 ns).

The cumulative distributions of the number of paths above threshold are shown in Figure 4 for the flat rural and urban high-rise cells. In the flat rural cell, approximately 1% of the APDPs show 17 or more paths and approximately 10% of the APDPs show 8 or more paths. In the urban high-rise cell, approximately 1% of the APDPs show 46 or more paths while approximately 10% of the APDPs show 33 or more paths.

These results give an idea of the number of required taps that may be needed to model the impulse response of the radio channel in different environments in the 1850-1990 MHz band. The urban high-rise cell would, of course, require more taps. It should be noted that a threshold of 20 dB below the peak in each APDP was used to define a path. Thresholds less than 20 dB below the peak would show less paths above threshold. Data for threshold levels of 3, 5, and 10 dB below the peak in each APDP are presented in [1].

The second set of statistics computed are the path arrival time statistics. These statistics give a description of the time-of-arrival of each path that exceeds a threshold for all APDPs within a cell that have a total of n paths (where n varies from 1 to 10). The results are displayed in tabular form where the mean and standard deviation of the arrival time for each individual path are presented. As an example of these results, Table 1 shows the time-of-arrival statistics for the flat rural cell. The table is organized so that each column represents all of the APDPs within a cell that have a total of n paths where n varies from 1 to 10. Each row represents a specific individual path for APDPs having a total of n paths.

For an example of the use of this table, choose the column with a total of 3 paths (n=3). The number of APDPs having a total of 3 paths was 765 out of a total number of 3220

APDPs in this cell. The first path always occurs at zero time, therefore its mean and standard deviation of arrival time are both zero. The mean arrival time of the second path is $0.14 \mu\text{s}$ and the standard deviation is $0.21 \mu\text{s}$. The mean arrival time of the third path is $0.75 \mu\text{s}$ and the standard deviation is $1.22 \mu\text{s}$.

5. CONCLUSIONS

The results of the spatial diversity analysis showed some, although not a large, decrease in RMS delay spread values using the diversity combination technique of selecting the lowest RMS delay spread between corresponding APDPs from both channels. These results suggest that the wideband signals seen on each channel were indeed uncorrelated to some degree. The urban high-rise cell showed a much higher probability of exceeding RMS delay spread values (up to $1.3 \mu\text{s}$) than the flat rural cell.

The multipath power statistics provided statistical information about the signal amplitude variation for every delay time for all of the APDPs in a given cell. These statistics showed that the urban high-rise cell had many more multipath components above threshold than the flat rural cell out to 4 or 5 μs in delay. The peak (normalized) multipath power was also higher (for delays greater than 15 μs) in the flat rural cell than in the urban high-rise cell.

The results of the number of paths analysis provide an idea of the number of required taps that may be needed to model the impulse response of the radio channel for PCS in different environments in the 1850-1990 MHz band. The results clearly showed that the urban high-rise cell would require a far greater number of taps than the flat rural cell. It should be noted that these results, and all of the results of the data analyses presented in this paper, are quite dependent on the threshold level used in processing; different results would be expected for different threshold levels. Time-of-arrival information in the form of mean and standard deviation of the arrival time of each individual path (up to 10 paths) should be quite beneficial in the design of impulse response models in cells similar to the flat rural cell used in this measurement experiment; it may not be adequate for cells similar to the urban high-rise cell. A further extension of this work might be to expand the time-of-arrival information out to 30 or 40 paths.

6. REFERENCES

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Figure 1. Cumulative distribution of RMS delay spread in the flat rural (a) and urban high-rise (b) cells.

Figure 2. Average and peak multipath power in the flat rural (a) and urban high-rise (b) cells.

Figure 3. Multipath power threshold statistics in the flat rural (a) and urban high-rise (b) cells.

Figure 4. Cumulative distribution of the number of paths.

Table 1. Mean (μ) and Standard Deviation (σ) of Path Arrival Time (in μs) Using a -20 dB Threshold for Each Individual Path for APDPs Having a Total of n Paths in the Flat Rural Cell

		Total Number of Paths n in APDP																			
		n = 1		n = 2		n = 3		n = 4		n = 5		n = 6		n = 7		n = 8		n = 9		n = 10	
Number of APDPs*		183		1058		765		410		236		130		102		60		64		45	
Individual Path #		μ	σ	μ	σ	μ	σ	μ	σ	μ	σ	μ	σ	μ	σ	μ	σ	μ	σ	μ	σ
1		0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
2				0.17	0.43	0.14	0.21	0.15	0.75	0.11	0.03	0.19	0.83	0.11	0.04	0.27	1.21	0.11	0.03	0.12	0.03
3						0.75	1.22	0.44	0.98	0.34	0.31	0.37	0.84	0.28	0.15	0.41	1.21	0.28	0.18	0.23	0.03
4								1.61	2.59	0.87	0.87	0.75	0.97	0.52	0.33	0.63	1.22	0.52	0.36	0.44	0.17
5										2.52	3.16	1.49	1.75	1.06	1.12	1.04	1.44	0.76	0.49	0.73	0.35
6												3.78	3.91	1.85	1.82	1.55	1.68	1.10	0.63	1.08	0.53
7														4.80	4.54	3.07	2.88	1.56	0.78	1.47	0.62
8																6.09	4.71	2.83	2.20	1.93	0.86
9																		5.52	4.57	2.79	1.76
10																				5.81	4.21

*The total number of APDPs in the flat rural cell was 3220.